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3 RIVER WATER DISINFECTION AND REMOVAL OF EMERGING CONTAMINANTS AND ANTIBIOTIC-
4 RESISTANT BACTERIA BY HETEROGENEOUS VISIBLE PHOTO-FENTON USING A BIMETALLIC NATURAL
5 CLINOPTILOLITE ZEOLITE

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31

32 **ABSTRACT**

33 The presence of contaminants of emerging concern and antibiotic-resistant bacteria in aquatic
34 environments is a major global challenge. Heterogeneous photo-Fenton-type treatments have proven
35 effective, but affordable and sustainable catalysts are needed for real-world water problems. For the
36 first time, we report the efficacy of a heterogeneous bimetallic Fe-Cu clinoptilolite catalyst, which is
37 able to remove up to 29 contaminants of emerging concern (pharmaceuticals, metabolites, industrial
38 products, herbicides, and insecticides) at concentrations ranging from 6.38 to 2358 ng/L and
39 inactivated naturally occurring bacteria from Guadaíra River water (Spain) to the detection limit of 1
40 CFU/100 mL. Heterogeneous photo-Fenton (1 g/L of NZ-Fe-Cu catalyst, 2.9 mM H₂O₂ and visible light:

41 410-710 nm / 9 W/m²) was the method selected for the targeted real water river treatment. The
42 successful synthesis of the material was demonstrated by X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transform
43 infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM/EDX). DR-UV-Vis measurements
44 allowed the estimation of the optical band gap, which was used to predict the photocatalytic
45 performance of the bimetallic zeolite. The photocatalytic mechanism of this new material was
46 investigated, including hydroxyl radical detection, reusability and stability (leaching) tests. Complete
47 inactivation of antibiotic-resistant bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* (initial
48 concentration $\approx 10^6$ CFU/mL) to the detection limit (50 CFU/mL) without further regrowth for 24 h was
49 achieved. These results highlight the potential of this new catalyst for the decontamination and
50 disinfection of river water, supporting its suitability for agricultural irrigation and its promising
51 applicability in broader wastewater treatment contexts.

52 **Keywords:** *contaminants of emerging concern, antibiotic-resistant bacteria, bimetallic catalyst, natural*
53 *zeolite, heterogeneous photo-Fenton*

54 1. INTRODUCTION

55 Currently, the presence of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) and antibiotic-resistant bacteria
56 (ARB) in aquatic systems represents a significant problem on a global scale [1,2]. The World Health
57 Organization (WHO) and other international agencies, such as the European Environment Agency (EEA)
58 and the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), have identified CECs and ARB in
59 wastewater as a growing threat to public health and the environment. CECs encompass a wide variety
60 of chemical compounds that are detected in the environment at trace concentrations, but they can
61 have significant adverse effects. These compounds originate from various sources, such as
62 pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, pesticides, and cleaning products, among others. Although many of these
63 compounds are widely used for their benefits in daily life, their persistence and ability to
64 bioaccumulate pose potential risks to aquatic ecosystems and human health [1]. Moreover, antibiotic
65 resistance is one of the greatest public health threats of the 21st century. Both CECs and ARB can be
66 found in effluents from wastewater treatment plants which often receive discharges from hospitals,
67 agricultural facilities, and households. Conventional treatment processes are not always capable of
68 completely eliminating these contaminants [3], allowing their release into water bodies and their
69 potential spread to the general population [4,5].

70 Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs) are gaining space as promising solution to face abatement of
71 CECs and ARB, as their high efficiency has been widely demonstrated [6–8] and its applicability has
72 been achieved at pilot and industrial scale [9,10]. AOPs generate reactive oxidant species, such as
73 hydroxyl radicals (\bullet OH), capable of degrading a wide range of organic contaminants into less harmful
74 compounds or even fully mineralizing them [11]. Different studies show the potential of AOPs not only
75 for CECs degradation but also for disinfection of water and the elimination of resistance genes, thus
76 helping to control the spread of multidrug-resistant pathogens in the environment [12,13]. Among
77 AOPs, the Fenton process and its variants have proven to be highly effective. However, the need to
78 operate under acidic conditions and the production of iron sludge are significant limitations of the
79 classical Fenton process. To overcome these limitations, the heterogeneous photo-Fenton process has
80 emerged as an innovative solution [14]. In this process, solid catalysts containing iron in their structure
81 are used, allowing the continuous regeneration of active iron and minimizing sludge production. In
82 addition, activating the process with visible light, which represents the largest fraction of the solar
83 spectrum, leverages a renewable and abundant energy source. This not only improves the efficiency
84 of the process but also makes it more sustainable and economically viable [14].

85 Numerous photo-Fenton catalysts have been used to treat contaminated water , such as clays, oxide
86 minerals, and metal-organic frameworks, among others [15,16]. To ensure that the process is as
87 sustainable as possible, investigations in this field should focus on the use of natural materials that are
88 abundant, low-cost and accessible. This is the case for natural zeolites, a widely available
89 aluminosilicate resource found globally. They have high ion exchange capacity, excellent adsorption
90 properties, significant selectivity for specific ions, and stability, making them ideal for water treatment
91 applications [17].

92 In contrast to toxic metals such as cobalt, manganese, and nickel, the synthesis of heterogeneous
93 catalysts based on copper and iron is more attractive due to their greater abundance and lower
94 toxicity [18]. Furthermore, it is known that the use of bimetallic systems based on Fe and Cu improves
95 the efficiency of the Fenton reaction since they favor the regeneration of Cu(II) and the production of
96 reactive oxygen species (ROS) that demonstrate better catalytic performance than their monometallic
97 counterparts [18,19]. The superior catalytic performance of bimetallic catalysts can be attributed to
98 an increase in surface area and/or the synergistic effect between metals [20] accelerating interfacial
99 electron transfer and enhancing the catalyst's performance in activating H₂O₂ [21]. As a result, the
100 development of bimetallic catalysts has become a key focus in Fenton chemistry. Composites of
101 bimetallic Fe and Cu compounds on zeolite surfaces, as identified by X-ray diffraction, have proven to
102 be good catalysts for Fenton-type processes. An 87% of bisphenol-A can be removed from wastewater
103 using copper chloride - iron oxide bimetallic catalysts supported on a synthetic zeolite [22]. Also, a
104 natural zeolite-supported multiphase composite of nano zero valent iron, FeO, Fe₂O₃, Fe₃C and
105 CuFeO₂ achieved more than 95% of trichloroethylene degradation efficiency used as a heterogeneous
106 Fenton like catalyst [23]. These papers do not provide evidence for the catalytic activity, if any, of
107 bimetallic exchanged zeolites as single-phase catalysts. Thus, it is clear that a distinction must be made
108 between composites and single-phase bimetallic zeolites. In the following, unless the term composite
109 is explicitly mentioned, we will refer to single-phase zeolites.

110 Numerous studies have shown that heterogeneous photo-Fenton processes effectively degrade
111 various micropollutants under controlled laboratory conditions, with contaminant concentrations on
112 the scale of milligrams per liter [24,25]. However, such 'high' concentrations (compared with the real
113 values found in the real polluted waters) do not accurately reflect those found in natural surface
114 waters. Recently, research has focused on the removal of micropollutants using water samples spiked
115 with model micropollutants. For example, iron-nickel bimetallic magnetic nano-alloy was
116 demonstrated to be an efficient heterogeneous photo-Fenton-like catalyst to remove phenol in tap
117 water and river water [26]. Also, a heterogeneous photo-Fenton catalyst tourmaline
118 TW10/PMS/Visible light system degraded up to 98.7% of tetracycline in seawater, Yellow River, and
119 Yangtze River water [27]. Only a limited number of studies have investigated micropollutants at low
120 concentrations in real water sources. However, these assays are crucial to evaluate the potential of
121 new catalysts in real-world applications, as field trials can help identify technology with local
122 limitations [28]. In a recent work, we prepared monometallic Fe- or Cu-exchanged natural zeolite
123 clinoptilolite, which showed good photocatalytic properties in the disinfection of saline solution
124 containing *E. coli* as a model pathogen [29]. As noted above, bimetallic Fe-Cu catalysts are gaining
125 attention due to their increased photocatalytic activity under visible light activity associated with the
126 reported stabilization of Fe-Cu pairs. This, together with our previous experience on monometallic
127 systems [29], opens a space for research. The application of bimetallic zeolites has not been used in
128 real applications involving the combined elimination of CECs and ARBs, nor in complex water matrices
129 such as natural surface water or wastewater.

130 The main goal of this work is to accomplish the disinfection and decontamination of water of real rivers
131 by heterogeneous photo-Fenton processes. To face this challenge, we turn here to a new
132 heterogeneous catalyst consisting of a bimetallic exchanged natural clinoptilolite (NZ-Fe-Cu). The
133 material was evaluated in the heterogeneous visible photo-Fenton treatment of Guadaíra River water
134 samples, in which the decontamination of a mixture of micro-pollutants (pharmaceuticals, pesticides,
135 etc.) and the inactivation of naturally occurring bacteria was studied. To gain a deeper understanding
136 of the performance of the new catalyst previously, decontamination and disinfection were evaluated
137 in synthetic waters under the same test conditions. Disinfection was also evaluated with two ARB
138 bacteria *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*. The hydroxyl radical production, catalyst reuse and leaching were
139 also evaluated.

140

141 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

142 **2.1. Chemicals Reagents**

143 Clinoptilolite was modified using ammonium chloride >99% purchased from PanReac, iron II sulfate
144 heptahydrated 99% and copper II nitrate trihydrated 99% from WVC. 30% Hydrogen peroxide
145 (PanReac) was used for heterogeneous photo-Fenton reactions. Naproxen sodium salt was purchased
146 from Merk). In disinfection experiments, catalase from bovine liver from Merk was used. Tryptone and
147 yeast extract (Condalab) and sodium chloride >99.9% (Labkem) were employed to prepare Luria-
148 Bertani (LB, 10 g/L tryptone, 5 g/L yeast extract and 5 g/L NaCl) culture medium. TTC Chapman Agar
149 obtained from Condalab was used as culture medium for total coliforms. LC-MS-grade acetonitrile,
150 methanol, and water were supplied by Romil Ltd. Analytical grade formic acid was obtained from
151 PanReac. Ammonium formate and ammonium acetate were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All
152 analytical standards were of high purity (>99.0%).

153 **2.2. Preparation of the zeolitic material**

154 The starting natural zeolite was obtained from the Tasajeras deposit (Villa Clara, Cuba) and was sieved
155 to obtain a particle size between 40-90 μm , followed by washes with distilled water at room
156 temperature and brought to boiling in the final wash. The purified zeolite (NZ) consists of a mixture of
157 clinoptilolite (70%), mordenite (5%), anorthite (15%) and quartz (10%) [30]. NZ was subjected to ion
158 exchange with ammonium chloride (0.5M) and calcined for 5 h at 450 °C to obtain an acid form and
159 maximize the transition metal incorporation, as reported by Garcia-Basabe *et al.* [31]. Then, two
160 exchanges processes (three cycles of each with fresh solution) were carried out at 80 °C, first, with
161 0.5M FeSO_4 and then with 0.5M $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and during 4 h. Finally, the sample was thoroughly washed
162 with distilled water to remove any remaining salt and oven-dried at 100°C.

163 **2.3. Characterization of zeolitic material**

164 The material was physicochemically characterized by XRD, FTIR, UV-Vis, SEM/EDX and ICP-AES (see
165 *Supplementary Information*). To perform a preliminary photocatalytic characterization of the material,
166 several decontamination and disinfection tests were performed using heterogeneous photo-Fenton
167 processes. A 1 L glass reactor with a double jacket for water recirculation at a constant temperature of
168 25°C and equipped with magnetic stirring (500 rpm) was used (Fig. S.1). The reactor was wrapped in
169 aluminium foil to enhance and homogenize the light distribution. A submersible visible light lamp was
170 used (410-710 nm / 9 W/m², emission spectra depicted in Fig. S.2). The necessary amounts of H₂O₂ and
171 zeolite were added to the reactor to have 2.9 mM of H₂O₂ and 1 g/L of NZ-Fe-Cu catalyst. The initial
172 pH was close to neutral without external adjustment in all experiments (pH \approx 7 in decontamination
173 tests, pH \approx 6 in disinfection in a saline solution of 0.9% w/v NaCl and pH \approx 8 in river water samples).

174 Decontamination tests with rhodamine B and naproxen were carried out by duplicate with an initial
175 concentration of both contaminants of 10 mg/L. Adsorption of both pollutants in NZ-Fe-Cu was
176 evaluated and controls i) without photocatalytic material (H₂O₂ and visible light), ii) with H₂O₂ alone
177 and iii) with visible light alone, were carried out. The concentration of rhodamine B and naproxen over
178 time was followed by UV-vis spectroscopy (554 nm) and HPLC (details in *Supplementary Information*),
179 respectively. To analyze •OH production using NZ-Fe-Cu as a catalyst, p-nitrosodimethylaniline (RNO;
180 17 μM) was employed as a probe and spin trap. The tests were conducted under the same conditions
181 as those used for photo-Fenton experiments. RNO concentration was monitored by UV-vis
182 spectroscopy at 440 nm.

183 Disinfection tests were performed in duplicate with an initial concentration of pathogens (*E. coli* strain
184 K12, *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 and *S. aureus* CDC47) of about 10⁶ CFU/mL. Before all disinfection tests, a
185 sample was taken to ensure that there were no microorganisms in the reactor or saline solution. In
186 addition, a sample was kept in the dark at room temperature and plated twice (at the beginning and
187 at the end of each experiment) to confirm the viability of the bacteria. A treated sample was also set
188 aside and plated twice, once at the time of sampling and once 24 h later, to ensure no bacterial post
189 treatment regrowth. The samples collected during the experiments were quantified using the standard
190 plate counting method, involving 10-fold serial dilutions in LB broth. To quench the action of H₂O₂ over
191 bacteria during the time interval between sampling and plating, the required amount of catalase
192 solution was added. Colonies were counted after incubation for 24 h at the appropriate temperature
193 (37°C for *E. coli* and 30°C for *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*). Each sample was processed in triplicate. The
194 detection limit for this method was 50 CFU/mL.

195 The reusability evaluation of the material in rhodamine B degradation and *E. coli* inactivation was
196 carried out in seven and three consecutive runs, respectively. Leached iron and copper can contribute
197 to homogeneous oxidation leading to disinfection or decontamination of water. To evaluate this,
198 homogeneous oxidation tests were carried out using the leachate. First, under the same conditions
199 described above, a suspension of bimetallic zeolite (1 g/L) was exposed to H₂O₂ and light for 3 h. The
200 resulting leachate was filtered through an 0.1 μm pore size membrane to remove the zeolite, and
201 rhodamine B or *E. coli* and H₂O₂ were added to have the same initial concentrations than in
202 heterogeneous test. The system was then illuminated for 3 h (degradation test) or 2 h (disinfection
203 test). In the disinfection test, the leachate was pre-sterilized.

204 To study the degradation kinetics of rhodamine B and naproxen, the experimental data were fitted
205 using the first and second order models, commonly used in Fenton-type reactions [32], and BMG
206 model (an empirical model for two-stage kinetics [33]). The corresponding equations are presented in
207 the *Supplementary Information*. For the disinfection processes, the experimental data were fitted
208 according to different models. The classical disinfection models reported in the literature are the Chick-
209 Watson first order equation, the Chick-Watson modified model, the Weibull model and the Geeraerd
210 model (see equations in the *Supplementary Information*). The correct application of Chick-Watson
211 model requires a constant disinfection rate throughout the process, although the initial delay in
212 bacterial inactivation could be attributed to a lag phase. In such cases, the delayed Chick-Watson
213 model, which includes an additional parameter, t₀ (representing the delay time), is more appropriate
214 for fitting experimental data [34]. In first-order models, microbial populations are assumed to be
215 homogeneous in resistance, while Weibull model considers them heterogeneous, with cell death
216 depending on the contact time with external stress [35]. Each cell requires different times to die, and
217 the variability in resistance follows a Weibull distribution. Geeraerd model is able to simulate
218 independently a smooth initiation (shoulder) and/or saturation (tail) of the decay [36].

219

220 2.4. River water treatment

221 River water from the Guadaíra River (Alcalá de Guadaíra, Spain) was collected, settled for 24 h,
222 decanted, and filtered to remove supernatant particles. The main physicochemical characteristics of
223 the pre-treated river water are shown in Table S.1. In decontamination assays, the raw water and the

224 zeolite (1 g/L) were added to the reactor in the dark and stirred at 500 rpm. Then, H₂O₂ was added to
225 the reactor (2.9 mM) and the lamp was turned on for 2 h. Before and after 2h-illumination samples
226 were taken to quantify existing CECs by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (see
227 *Supplementary Information*). Furthermore, total coliforms were measured every 30 min for the
228 runtime of the photo-Fenton test using the standard plate counting method described before. The
229 same test was repeated, but only the initial and final concentrations of *E. coli* and coliforms were
230 evaluated. To identify and quantify *E. coli* and coliform bacteria with minimal bacterial background
231 interference, 100 mL of water sample was filtered through a 0.45 μm pore diameter filter membrane,
232 transferred to a special chromogenic medium (Chromatic™ Coliform Agar ISO) plate and incubated
233 aerobically at 36 ± 2°C for 24 h. The detection limit for this method was 1 CFU/100mL.

234

235 3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

236 3.1. Characterization of bimetallic natural zeolite

237 3.1.1. Physicochemical characterization

238 XRD was applied to confirm the successful synthesis of NZ-Fe-Cu (Fig. 1a). The NZ pattern confirms that
239 the primary zeolitic phases are clinoptilolite and mordenite and that the method used to obtain the
240 catalyst does not affect the zeolitic structure, only changes in the relative intensity of some reflections
241 are observed due to cation exchange. In addition, the occurrence of secondary supported phases was
242 not observed. The conditions under which the photo-Fenton treatment takes place and the reagents
243 used do not affect the structure of the catalyst (Fig. S.3). FT-IR spectra of the samples also show that
244 there are no structural changes in clinoptilolite when iron and copper cations are incorporated, but
245 neither when the catalyst is used in the photocatalytic treatment (Fig. 1b). Bands characteristic of the
246 zeolite at 460, 605, 720, 795, and 1062 cm⁻¹ are due to the vibration of the stretching, bending and
247 rocking of the Al-O-Si bridge [37]. Water molecularly bound in the zeolitic structure as well as the
248 metal-O bonding gives a band at 1645 cm⁻¹. The peak at 3460 cm⁻¹ corresponds to symmetric and
249 asymmetric stretching of the hydroxyl group due to absorbed water.

250

251
 252 **Figure 1.** (a) XRD powder patterns of the starting zeolite NZ and the iron-copper exchanged
 253 clinoptilolite NZ-Fe-Cu. Simulated patterns of clinoptilolite (CLI) and mordenite (MOR) reported by the
 254 *International Zeolite Association*, are also shown for comparison. Peaks that change their relative
 255 intensity after treatments are indicated with an asterisk. (b) FT-IR spectra of NZ and the prepared
 256 catalyst before (NZ-Fe-Cu) and after photo-Fenton inactivation of *E. coli* (NZ-Fe-Cu post vis).

257 SEM micrographs (Fig. S.4a and b) show that NZ-Fe-Cu has rough-surface particles with lamellar of
 258 smooth edges morphology, which are arranged in stacks within the mineral, forming compact
 259 aggregates of around 90 μm . There is no modification in the particle's morphology after the
 260 photocatalytic treatment. As an example, the catalyst is shown after an *E. coli* inactivation cycle (Fig.
 261 S.4c and d). Elemental analysis (Table S.4) revealed the incorporation of Cu and Fe into NZ-Fe-Cu.
 262 Specifically, the iron content increased from 1.81% to 8.84%, while copper, which is absent in the NZ,
 263 was incorporated at around 4%.

264 Figure 2 shows the diffuse reflectance UV-vis spectra of NZ and bimetallic zeolite before and after one
 265 cycle of photo-Fenton inactivation of *E. coli*. The spectrum of NZ shows bands at 215, 265, 360 and 740
 266 nm that correspond to charge-transfer complex due to the interaction of exchangeable cations with
 267 ligand water molecules and/or with the zeolite framework, oxygen bound to the aluminium
 268 framework, Fe^{3+} in octahedral environment, and Fe^{2+} ion transitions or Fe^{2+} - Fe^{3+} inter-valence charge
 269 transfer, respectively [38,39]. After the iron exchange processes (sample NZ-Fe-Cu) the absorbance of
 270 all bands increases, a new band at 481 nm appears and the band at 740 nm shifts to a higher
 271 wavelength. It has been reported for copper exchange clinoptilolite that bands in the wavelength range
 272 from 300 to 500 nm correspond to the presence of copper in the form of Cu_xO [40]. The shift of the
 273 band at 740 nm can be attributed to Cu^{2+} cations in octahedral coordination [41].

274

275 **Figure 2.** UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectra of NZ and sample exchanged with iron and copper (NZ-Fe-
 276 Cu) before and after one cycle of photo-Fenton inactivation of *E. coli* with visible light.

277 Band gap energy (E_g) of the samples estimated using the Tauc plot method (Fig. S.5) for allowed direct
 278 ($n = \frac{1}{2}$) and allowed indirect ($n = 2$) transitions are shown in Table S.5. The band gaps obtained for NZ
 279 (2.52-2.29) are lower than that theoretically expected (5.59) for an idealized clinoptilolite [42] due to
 280 iron impurities (see Table 1). Transition metal doping introduces intermediate bands which reduces
 281 the band gap up to 2.03 ($n = 1/2$) and 2.12 ($n = 2$), improving the light absorption in the visible region
 282 and thus, larger amount of sunlight can be utilized. Previous studies have shown that Cu doping can
 283 effectively reduce the band gap of the catalyst due to the presence of d orbitals and can also act as
 284 active electron traps to reduce electron-hole recombination [43]. The doping process with iron
 285 prevents the recombination of electron-hole pairs, thereby enhancing the activation and formation of
 286 ROS [43,44]. It is also important to note that the band gap remains stable after subjecting the material
 287 to one treatment cycle of *E. coli* inactivation (Table S.5).

288

289 3.1.2. Photocatalytic characterization

290 The efficiency of bimetallic clinoptilolite in the degradation of two model contaminants (rhodamine B
 291 and naproxen) was tested. Rhodamine B has been widely used as a model pollutant in photo-Fenton
 292 tests because of its high photostability and good representativeness as an industrial pollutant, as well
 293 as its known degradation mechanism and ease of handling [45]. This molecule is slightly adsorbed on
 294 the clinoptilolite surface, so the zeolite/rhodamine B system was allowed to equilibrate in the dark for
 295 about 90 min before the photo-Fenton tests, where the stability of the adsorbed amount was observed
 296 (about 20% of the initial concentration). Rhodamine B is practically not degraded when subjected to
 297 visible light, H_2O_2 and the synergistic effect of both (Fig 3a). Degradation efficiency increases to almost
 298 80% when bimetallic zeolite is added to the reaction medium, demonstrating the photocatalytic
 299 efficiency of the material (Fig. 3a). The behavior of the material in the degradation of the CEC naproxen
 300 was also studied (Fig. 3b). In this case, only 5% of the drug is adsorbed in the 60 min that the system
 301 was allowed to equilibrate in the dark. This is due to differences in the functional groups of the two
 302 molecules. Rhodamine B has amino groups that can be positively charged at the working pH, thus
 303 favoring the interaction of these groups with the zeolite surface which has a negative charge density.

304 Naproxen on the other hand has a carboxyl group, so the interaction with the zeolite surface is not
 305 favored. In addition, rhodamine B has a larger structure with several functional groups and a larger
 306 aromatic system. Naproxen practically does not degrade when treated with H₂O₂ or visible light alone.
 307 However, the degradation is higher (70%) in the presence of both H₂O₂ and visible radiation, indicating
 308 that this molecule is more labile than rhodamine B under the conditions employed. When hydrogen
 309 peroxide is combined with visible radiation, several ROS are formed due to the photolysis of H₂O₂, such
 310 as •OH and superoxide radical (•O₂⁻), among others [46,47]. When the catalyst is added, a complete
 311 and much faster naproxen degradation is achieved in 3 h (Fig. 3b). The kinetic curves for both
 312 molecules are well described by the first-order and BMG models, with correlation coefficients close to
 313 or greater than 0.99, while the second-order model shows a deviation from the data (Figure S.6 and
 314 Table S.6). Both curves show a rapid degradation of the contaminant in the first 60 min, followed by a
 315 slower degradation rate. The initial degradation rate (1/m) for naproxen (0.025 min⁻¹) is higher than
 316 that for rhodamine B (0.008 min⁻¹). These results show the efficiency of the synthesized material for
 317 the degradation of organic molecules. However, future work should undertake the study of total
 318 mineralization since many degradation intermediates are more toxic than the original pollutant as is
 319 the case for rhodamine B [48] and naproxen [49].

320
 321 **Figure 3.** Degradation of (a) rhodamine B and (b) naproxen by heterogeneous photo-Fenton with
 322 visible light using the bimetallic zeolitic catalyst. The continuous lines correspond to the BMG model
 323 fit.

324
 325 Degradation assays were also carried out with the organic dye stuff RNO. This is a widely used as an
 326 easy detectable probe compound and spin trap for the detection of particular •OH in photo-Fenton
 327 studies, as it neither reacts with singlet oxygen (¹O₂), superoxide anions (O₂⁻) nor other peroxy
 328 compounds [50]. In this work, under the conditions tested, we didn't detect any significant formation
 329 of •OH (just 2%) when there was no NZ-Fe-Cu in the reaction medium (Fig. 4). This finding aligns with
 330 previous research indicating that, without a catalytic agent, the reaction between H₂O₂ and visible light
 331 generates only minimal ROS, insufficient for efficient organic compound degradation [51].

332 The degradation of 70% of naproxen in the absence of catalyst (Fig. 3b) could be due to other ROS
333 generated by the synergetic effect of H₂O₂ and visible light, possibly ¹O₂ or O₂⁻. Photolysis is ruled out
334 as a significant pathway in our experimental setup, as demonstrated by control experiments, where
335 visible light alone failed to induce measurable naproxen degradation. Although Vulava *et al.* [52]
336 reported a relatively rapid photodegradation of naproxen in direct sunlight (half-life of 53 min), the
337 discrepancy in our results may stem from differences in light wavelength and intensity, as visible light
338 lacks the high-energy UV component crucial for direct photolysis.

339 In contrast, when the catalyst is added, a significant production of •OH is detected (Fig. 4), confirming
340 its key role in promoting ROS generation. Other systems using zeolites in heterogeneous photo-Fenton
341 tests have also shown that the main degradation mechanism is based on the action of •OH. For
342 example, Tammaro *et al.* [53] found that •OH play the main role in the removal of phenol under solar
343 light using composite of nano-sized Fe₃O₄ entrapped in Y zeolite. In addition, Gao *et al.* [45] showed
344 that •OH were crucial for the degradation of rhodamine B in the visible light photo-Fenton process
345 using Fe-supported bentonite. Therefore, our results, in line with others previously described, highlight
346 the effectiveness of the catalytic material in promoting the generation of •OH, resulting in significantly
347 improved degradation rates compared to non-catalyzed systems.

348
349 **Figure 4.** Degradation of p-nitrosodimethylaniline (RNO) by •OH generated with visible light in the
350 absence and presence of the catalyst.

351 The results shown in Fig. 5 demonstrate that NZ-Fe-Cu has a high capacity as a photocatalyst for
352 bacterial inactivation. The disinfection efficiency of the material was tested by heterogeneous photo-
353 Fenton inactivation of a model bacteria (*E. coli*) and two bacteria known for their capacity to develop
354 resistance to multiple antibiotics (*P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*). When the material is not present, only
355 slightly more than 1-log inactivation was achieved for the three bacteria. This reduction in bacterial
356 concentration is explained by the synergic effect of the combination of visible light and H₂O₂, and the
357 cellular self-defense mechanisms are sufficient to handle the stresses produced under these operating
358 conditions [54]. Initially, the cell membrane is compromised by the oxidative effect of H₂O₂, which has
359 a polarity similar to that of water, allowing its diffusion into the bacteria and triggers a lipid
360 peroxidation chain reaction. This reaction increases membrane permeability and threatens bacterial
361 viability. Additionally, cells already partially damaged by this oxidative stress are exposed to visible
362 light, increasing lethality [55]. Other authors have also reported that the combined effect of H₂O₂ (5
363 mM) and visible light was almost negligible for *E. coli* and *S. aureus* inactivation in 40 min [56].

364 Subramanian and Prakash found that H₂O₂ (2 mM) alone, in dark or under visible light irradiation, did
365 not affect cell viability of *E. coli*, *S. aureus* or *P. aeruginosa* [57].

366 In the presence of the catalyst, inactivation of the three bacteria to the detection limit (50 CFU/mL) is
367 achieved by heterogeneous photo-Fenton treatment, with log-reduction of 4.33-log, 3.57-log and
368 4.54-log for *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*, respectively. The performance of photocatalytic
369 disinfection in saline solution containing *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* is very similar, reaching complete
370 inactivation of both pathogens in only 1 h. However, the inactivation of *S. aureus* is achieved 30 min
371 later. Disinfection by the photo-Fenton process may show differences in its efficacy due to differences
372 in the structural and physiological characteristics of these bacteria. *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* are Gram-
373 negative bacteria which have a cell wall composed of a lipopolysaccharide-rich outer membrane, a thin
374 peptidoglycan layer, and a cytoplasmic membrane [58]. The outer membrane can act as an additional
375 protective barrier [59], hindering the entry of ROS. Consequently, an initial delay in the inactivation
376 curve of both bacteria is observed (Fig. 5) due to the time it takes for the cells to show the effect of
377 the damage caused by the photocatalytic process. This stage is then followed by a linear phase,
378 continuing until the detection limit is achieved. The inactivation of both bacteria by photo-Fenton
379 follows similar kinetic processes as can be seen in the kinetic fit's parameters presented in Table 1.
380 The experimental data in both cases can be well described by Weibull model, with correlations
381 coefficients of 0.9987 and 0.9793 for *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*, respectively. The shape parameter (*p*)
382 is higher than 1, which is coherent with the initial delay in the inactivation curves. *S. aureus* is a Gram-
383 positive bacterium, with a thicker cell wall consisting mainly of peptidoglycan and teichoic acids, but
384 without the outer membrane [58]. This structural difference may make Gram-positive bacteria more
385 susceptible to oxidative damage due to the lack of the additional protective barrier [60]. Consequently,
386 *S. aureus* may be more easily permeabilized by ROS, resulting in greater susceptibility to treatment in
387 the first minutes, thus, the initial delay in the inactivation curve for this microorganism is not observed.
388 On the other hand, the curve has a bimodal shape that is better described by the Geeraerd model
389 (Table 1). Furthermore, biological internal repair mechanisms are not sufficient to prevent ROS damage
390 in the three bacteria, as no bacterial regrowth occurred within 24 h (data not shown). Therefore, it can
391 be concluded that NZ-Fe-Cu causes irreversible damage to bacteria.

392
393 **Figure 5.** Inactivation of microorganisms by photo-Fenton with visible light using the zeolitic catalyst.
394 DL (detection limit) = 50 CFU/mL.

395

396 **Table 1:** Kinetic parameters of the experimental data fitted according to different models.

Kinetic model	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
Chick-Watson	K = 0.14±0.01 R ² = 0.8847	K = 0.12±0.02 R ² = 0.7197	K = 0.095±0.005 R ² = 0.9289
Chick-Watson modified	K = 0.16±0.02 t ₀ = 7±5 R ² = 0.8940	K = 0.16±0.04 t ₀ = 10±8 R ² = 0.7052	K = 0.09±0.01 t ₀ = 0 R ² = 0.9147
Weibull	Δ = 18.9±0.6 p = 1.97±0.06 R² = 0.9987	Δ = 30±3 p = 3.5±0.5 R² = 0.9793	Δ = 13±4 p = 1.1±0.2 R ² = 0.9251
Geeraerd	C ₀ = 1.09±0.05 (x10 ⁶) C _{res} = 0 K _{max} = 0.054±0.009 R ² = 0.9870	C ₀ = 1.8±0.3 (x10 ⁶) C _{res} = 0 K _{max} = 0.03±0.02 R ² = 0.8835	C ₀ = 4.83±0.06 (x10 ⁵) C _{res} = 6.2±0.3 (x10 ³) K _{max} = 0.143±0.008 R² = 0.9988

397

398 In previous studies by our group, the disinfection performance of monometallic natural clinoptilolite
399 catalysts, NZ-Fe and NZ-Cu, was evaluated. These catalysts reached the detection limit for *E. coli*
400 inactivation in 120 and 105 min, respectively [29]. This demonstrated their individual effectiveness, but
401 also suggested room for improvement in reaction efficiency. In the present study, the bimetallic
402 clinoptilolite catalyst (NZ-Fe-Cu) significantly reduced the time required for *E. coli* inactivation,
403 reaching the detection limit in only 60 min (half the time required by the monometallic counterparts).
404 This result highlights the remarkable synergy between Fe and Cu in the bimetallic system, likely due to
405 enhanced redox cycling between the Fe and Cu active sites, which enhances the catalytic
406 decomposition of hydrogen peroxide and the generation of ROS. Such synergistic effects highlight the
407 advantages of combining transition metals in catalysts to improve disinfection efficiency and optimize
408 advanced oxidation processes such as the heterogeneous photo-Fenton reaction.

409 Investigating the ability of a material to be reused in water treatment is essential to ensure the
410 efficiency, sustainability, cost-effectiveness and safety of the process. Therefore, several rhodamine B
411 decontamination cycles were carried out to evaluate the reusability of NZ-Fe-Cu. The results show that
412 the degradation capacity is maintained over seven treatment cycles (Fig. 6). The reusability of the
413 catalyst in consecutive disinfection cycles was also tested for *E. coli* (Fig. S.7). In this case, although the
414 material maintains some catalytic activity, the limit of detection is not reached within 2 h of the
415 experiment for cycles 2 and 3. This decrease in performance is attributed to the presence of NaCl in
416 the reaction media, necessary to maintain the osmotic balance of the cells, which promotes ionic
417 exchange between sodium ions (Na⁺) and the active metal cations (Fe⁺² and Cu⁺²) in the catalyst. Such
418 ion exchange compromises the availability of active sites, as has been found in similar studies of
419 heterogeneous catalysts used in saline environments [61,62]. This is demonstrated by more
420 pronounced loss of iron and copper from the material in the presence of NaCl (2.05 w% and 1.04 w%,
421 respectively; Table 2). In fact, after the first cycle, an increase in the sodium content from 0.38 to 3.45
422 % was detected in the catalyst by EDX in line with the Fe and Cu leaching observed. Moreover, chloride
423 ions (Cl⁻) can react with •OH to form secondary chlorine radicals (such as Cl•, Cl₂•⁻, and ClOH•⁻), which
424 have lower oxidative potential. This interaction reduces the availability of •OH for bacteria
425 inactivation, leading to an additional decrease in the efficiency of the reaction system [61]. This shows
426 that the catalytic material cannot be reused in saline solution and that future research should be
427 carried out to avoid cation exchange. On the contrary, in the absence of NaCl it was found that copper
428 and iron leach slightly from the catalyst (0.8 w% and 0.07 w%, respectively; Table 4). Despite the low

429 loss of metals, it should be noted that there is no detriment in the catalytic efficiency, so the material
 430 can be reused, thus ensuring the operability of the treatment system.

431
 432 **Figure 6.** Consecutive cycles for rhodamine B degradation by heterogeneous photo-Fenton using NZ-
 433 Fe-Cu and degradation efficiency (inset).

434
 435 **Table 2:** Amount of iron and copper in the catalyst before and after the first cycle of photo-Fenton
 436 degradation of rhodamine B and *E. coli* inactivation determined by ICP.

Sample	Fe (w%)	Cu (w%)
NZ-Fe-Cu	3.04	1.65
NZ-Fe-Cu after rhodamine B degradation	2.24	1.58
NZ-Fe-Cu after <i>E. coli</i> inactivation	0.99	0.61

437
 438 In order to distinguish the contribution of the catalyst (heterogeneous photo-Fenton) from that of the
 439 leached metals (homogeneous photo-Fenton), the degradation of rhodamine B and the inactivation of
 440 *E. coli* were evaluated with the filtered water after iron and copper leaching. The results were very
 441 revealing, showing that in the case of rhodamine B degradation, the iron and copper leachates in the
 442 presence of H₂O₂ and light, could not carry out the catalytic oxidation of the pollutant (Fig. 7).
 443 Therefore, it can be concluded that the oxidation of rhodamine B (Fig. 3A) is entirely due to the
 444 performance of the heterogeneous catalyst NZ-Fe-Cu. On the other hand, complete inactivation of *E.*
 445 *coli* is obtained with the leachate, even under better conditions than in the presence of zeolite,
 446 reaching the detection limit in 45 min (Fig. 7). Therefore, *E. coli* inactivation is clearly due to the
 447 combined effect of homogeneous and heterogeneous photo-Fenton processes. This can be due to the
 448 scattering and light absorption effect caused by the presence of the bimetallic zeolite, which reduces
 449 the efficiency of the process. This phenomenon is commonly reported for heterogeneous photo-
 450 Fenton processes and similar systems using particulate catalysts. For example, titanium dioxide (TiO₂)
 451 is known to increase turbidity in suspensions, which decreases the penetration of light, reducing the

452 overall photocatalytic efficiency [63]. Moreover, catalysts can agglomerate in aqueous systems, further
 453 increasing the scattering effect [64] and blocking the light required for optimal ROS generation. This
 454 effect is more pronounced when the catalyst concentration is high [64] and it could be avoided by
 455 carrying out ultrafine separation although it is challenging, requiring significant time and cost.
 456 However, the penetration depth of light is reduced because the catalyst particles block the incident
 457 light, creating a shadow effect [65]. To mitigate these effects, future research will focus on optimizing
 458 catalyst particle size and concentration, as well as exploring immobilized catalyst systems to maintain
 459 light transmission.

460
 461 **Figure 7.** Degradation of rhodamine B and inactivation of *E. coli* by NZ-Fe-Cu (heterogeneous photo-
 462 Fenton) and by leached iron and copper (homogeneous photo-Fenton).

463
 464 **3.2. River water treatment**

465 Finally, the main objective of this work was the evaluation of the efficacy of NZ-Fe-Cu in the treatment
 466 of river water. Therefore, the efficiency of bimetallic zeolite in the decontamination of 29 pollutants
 467 detected in a local river (Guadaíra River) covering pharmaceuticals, metabolites, industrial products,
 468 herbicides, and insecticides was studied (Fig. 8). Pharmaceuticals, including non-steroidal anti-
 469 inflammatory drugs, antiepileptics, b-blockers, nerve stimulants, lipid regulators, antihypertensives,
 470 and antibiotics, were found in low concentrations varying between 6.38 and 2358 ng/L. In this group,
 471 of the 16 drugs detected, half of them were eliminated with efficiencies between 74 and 95% and the
 472 most difficult to degrade were bezafibrate and ketoprofen with less than 15% of elimination.
 473 Additionally, the degradation of 1,7-dimethylxanthine (metabolite of caffeine), 3-
 474 hydroxycarbamazepine (metabolite of carbamazepine) and 4-hydroxycyclofenac (metabolite of
 475 diclofenac) was evaluated. These three metabolites share important characteristics related to their
 476 pharmaceutical origin, as well as their persistence in the environment and resistance to degradation,
 477 which makes them commonly present in rivers and their removal significant. 3-hydroxycarbamazepine
 478 was degraded up to 80% of the initial concentration and the concentration of the other two was
 479 reduced by approximately half. Perfluoropentanoic acid is a compound belonging to the PFAS family
 480 which was detected at an initial concentration in the river of 5.7 ng/L. PFAs are known for their high
 481 stability and persistence in the environment, with potential health and environmental risks, which has

482 led to a growing interest in their regulation and control [66]. Despite its proven persistence,
 483 photocatalytic treatment with bimetallic zeolite succeeded in reducing its initial concentration by 44%.
 484 However, the photocatalytic treatment could not significantly degrade other industrial pollutants such
 485 as decyl-, undecyl-, and dodecylbenzene sulfonate, probably due to the high concentrations found in
 486 the river (10.1, 6.5 and 2.3 mg/L, respectively) which are three orders of magnitude higher than the
 487 other pollutants monitored. Ultimately, low efficiency was achieved for the insecticides
 488 chlorfenvinphos, imidacloprid and acetamiprid, as well as for the herbicides diuron and terbutylazine,
 489 but the initial concentration of the herbicide terbutryn was reduced by half, from 20.1 to 10.7 ng/L.
 490 These results demonstrate the high capacity of NZ-Fe-Cu to degrade a complex mixture of pollutants
 491 present in river water in only 2 h.

492
 493 **Figure 8.** Simultaneous removal of 29 pollutants detected in Guadaíra River by heterogeneous photo-
 494 Fenton with bimetallic zeolite (pharmaceuticals in red, metabolites in pink, industrial products in blue,
 495 and herbicides, and insecticides in green bars) and without bimetallic zeolite (in black bars).

496 The capacity of the bimetallic catalyst to disinfect river water was also evaluated. It is important to
 497 note that in only 30 min of photocatalytic treatment, the concentration of total coliforms present in
 498 the river water was reduced to the limit of detection, compared to the test without zeolite, where the

499 combined effect of H₂O₂ and visible radiation only achieved to reduce the initial concentration of
 500 microorganisms in the water by 2-log (Fig. 9). Likewise, no bacterial regrowth was observed after 24 h,
 501 demonstrating the effectiveness of the treatment. Total coliforms are generally harder to inactivate
 502 than *E. coli* because they encompass a variety of bacterial species as *Citrobacter*, *Enterobacter*,
 503 *Escherichia*, *Hafnia*, *Klebsiella*, *Pantoea*, *Raoultella*, *Serratia*, *Yersinia* and occasionally other genera
 504 [67], some with higher resistance to disinfectants. Studies have shown that while *E. coli* is usually more
 505 susceptible to treatments as chlorination and UV radiation, total coliforms may require longer
 506 exposure times or higher doses of disinfectants for complete inactivation [68–70]. However, the initial
 507 bacterial concentration significantly influences the efficiency of photocatalytic water disinfection. High
 508 starting levels require extended inactivation times [71], whereas low initial levels can be inactivated in
 509 relatively short times. In the present work, the concentration of total coliforms in the real water
 510 experiments is much lower than the initial concentration of *E. coli* in the saline water experiments,
 511 which could explain the shorter inactivation times.

512 Finally, to evaluate the inactivation of *E. coli* from the river, the same assay was repeated, but only the
 513 initial and final concentrations were measured using a chromogenic medium to identify and quantify
 514 *E. coli* and coliform bacteria before and after treatment. In this test, the detection limit was also
 515 reduced to determine whether the treated water met the criteria for reuse. The water was collected
 516 at the same location but on a different day, so the initial coliform concentration differs slightly (1.4×10^5
 517 CFU/100mL). The initial *E. coli* concentration was 7.4×10^4 CFU/100mL. After 2 h of treatment, total
 518 inactivation of coliforms and *E. coli* was achieved until the detection limit of the method (1 CFU/100
 519 mL). Final concentration of *E. coli* ≤ 10 CFU/100 mL and validation target were met as disinfection
 520 targets for EU Regulation 2020/741 are set at ≥ 5 log units for bacteria or absence if not present in
 521 sufficient quantity to achieve the required log reduction. Therefore, water treated with NZ-Fe-Cu
 522 meets both disinfection requirements for use in agricultural irrigation. Furthermore, it is very
 523 important to note that the water resulting from this treatment would be considered the highest quality
 524 water according to this legislation (Class A; EU, 2020) and is therefore suitable for raw food crops in
 525 direct contact with reclaimed water and root crops.

526
 527 **Figure 9.** (a) Inactivation of total coliforms in Guadaíra River by photo-Fenton with visible light with
 528 and without bimetallic zeolitic catalyst. The error bars were calculated from three independent

529 counting of bacteria colonies. DL (detection limit) = 50 CFU/mL. (b) Chromogenic medium plates
530 seeded with Guadaíra River without treatment (top; dilution 1/10) and treated by photo-Fenton with
531 NZ-Fe-Cu (bottom; DL = 1 CFU/100mL).

532

533 CONCLUSIONS

534 This work demonstrates that the bimetallic Fe-Cu natural clinoptilolite is a promising catalyst for the
535 heterogeneous photo-Fenton treatment under visible light of real contaminated surface/river water.
536 Modified zeolite degraded a mixture of 29 contaminants of emerging concern in concentrations
537 ranging from ng/L to mg/L and efficiently inactivated total coliforms and *E. coli* present in a local river.
538 The material also demonstrated good performance in the inactivation of two antibiotic-resistant
539 bacteria; *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*) with no observed regrowth 24 h after the end of the tests. Due
540 to the hazardous nature of these bacteria, the material represents an important advance for global
541 health through advanced water treatment processes.

542 Modification of the natural zeolite clinoptilolite to incorporate iron and copper as extra-framework
543 charge balancing cations by a simple and economical hydrothermal process was proven to maintain
544 sufficient concentrations of both metals for successful photocatalytic performance in heterogeneous
545 mode with low metal leaching with no catalytic contribution from leachates. Scavenger tests
546 demonstrated a significant production of •OH which explain the high photo-oxidation activity of the
547 catalyst. Moreover, the reusability of this material was demonstrated by several degradation cycles.

548 The kinetic study shows that this bimetallic material achieves a catalytic activity that cuts treatment
549 times in half compared to its monometallic counterparts. This highlights the potential of the new
550 bimetallic natural zeolite as excellent candidate as sustainable catalysts for heterogeneous photo-
551 Fenton reactions, effectively treating complex water matrices while producing water that meets high-
552 quality standards for agricultural use. Future research will build on this study to explore chemical
553 engineering aspects to assess the potential scale-up of the process for real-world wastewater
554 treatment plants considering economic criteria.

555

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572

573 **Declaration of competing interest**

574 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships
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576

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